

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B148
Date: 12 Dec 2005
Take Off 09:48:05
Landing: 15:05:43
Flight Time 5h17m43

Campaign: Buncefield Smoke Experiment
Operating Area: South coast

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Roberts	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Graham Morgan	Directflight
3	CCM	Gaynor Ottaway	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist	Clare Lee	Met Office
5	Flight Manger	Ruth Purvis	FAAM
6	Core Chemistry	Alan Woolley	FAAM
7	Cloud Physics / CCM2	Jim Crawford	FAAM
8	ARIES training	Stuart Newman	Met Office
9	ARIES training	Stuart Rogers	Met Office
10	SWS	Dave Kindred	Met Office
11	SWS	Martin Glew	Met Office
12			
13			
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Flight Track:

B148 Track 12-DEC-05

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No b148
 Date: 12 Dec 2005
 Project: Buncefield Smoke Experiment
 Location: South coast

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
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094805		T/O			
095124		ASP open	5.5 kft	032	
100258		cameras	22.4 kft	062	started recording
100730	100858	Orbit 1	24.0 kft	055	left
100959	101139	Orbit 2	24.1 kft	322	left
101301	101446	Orbit 3	24.2 - 24.0 kft	257	left
101620	101804	Orbit 4	24.2 kft	162	left
101942	102343	Profile 1	24.0 - 20.4 kft	056	interrupt FL210
102024		bbr	23.3 kft	056	extended
102517	103041	Profile 1	20.3 - 14.4 kft	188	interrupt FL150
103251	103730	Profile 1	14.4 - 10.5 kft	357	interrupt FL110
103525		qnh 1034	12.3 kft	357	
103944	104614	Profile 1	10.5 - 4.0 kft	175	
104642	113636	Run 1	4.0 kft	179	4000ft
104656		qnh 1034	4.0 kft	179	
104814		bbr	4.0 kft	180	retracted
110846		camera	3.4 kft	239	dfc tape changed
111849		cameras	3.4 kft	277	DFC changed to FFC
113015		cameras	3.4 kft	226	upc tape changed
113636	113731	Profile 2	4.0 - 3.5 kft	223	3500ft
113742		qnh	3.5 kft	222	1032
113731	114406	Run 2	3.5 kft	222	3500ft
114417	114925	Profile 3	3.5 - 8.0 kft	273	
114458		bbr	4.0 kft	276	retracted
114925	120703	Run 3	8.0 kft	271	
120704	121024	Profile 4	8.0 - 5.0 kft	357	
121124	121725	Run 4	5.0 kft	075	
121732	122012	Profile 5	5.0 - 3.0 kft	076	3000ft
122435	122851	Run 5.1	3.0 kft	106	
123139	125033	Run 5.2	3.0 kft	257	
125302	130152	Run 5.3	3.0 kft	063	
130259	130414	Profile 6	3.4 - 5.0 kft	072	130208 bbr extend
130425	130856	Run 6	5.0 kft	074	
131033	131313	Profile 7	4.5 - 7.0 kft	263	
131413	131612	Profile 8	7.2 - 5.4 kft	266	
131832	132159	Run 7	5.0 kft	087	
132207	132447	Profile 9	5.0 - 3.0 kft	088	qnh 1033
132456	142707	Run 8	3.0 kft	086	3000ft
142745	143451	Profile 10	3.0 - 10.0 kft	338	
144409	144541	Orbit 5	20.1 - 20.0 kft	320	
144907		asp shut	16.0 kft	241	
150543		Land		288	
151016		final position			52'04.36N 0'37.50W

B148 Track 12-DEC-05

4°W 3°W 2°W 1°W 0° 1°E 2°E 3°E

Oil Fire Sortie

B148 - 12th December 2005

10:00	Take Off and transit to operating area at FL200	45
10:45	Perform 4 orbits at 45 deg banking angle	10
10:55	Profile descent to 1000ft at 1000ft/min to 5000ft then 500ft/min	25
11:20	Straight and level along AMPEP route clockwise until point to be defined nominally North Devon	70
12:30	Profile ascent to 4000ft	5
12:35	Straight and level along return AMPEP route (anticlockwise)	70
13:45	Profile ascent to FL200	25
14:10	Perform 4 orbits at 45 deg banking angle	10
14:20	Transit back to Cranfield	45
15:05	Land at Cranfield	

Mission Scientist Debrief

B148 – 12th December 2005

Smoke Fire Sortie

Mission scientist – Clare Lee

This was the first flight to study the smoke from the Buncefield fuel depot fire at Hemel Hempstead. Due to air traffic restrictions the notam area F was used, to go East from Cranfield, around the English channel, and then to come North into Devon where profiles can be made. Note the majority of this route is limited to maximum altitude of approx 5000ft. During this flight maneuvers to test the SWS were also flown.

There was generally 2 layers of cloud from 2000ft to 4000ft and at approx 8000ft

A transit to the NE of Norfolk was made climbing to FL240 to ensure that the aircraft was well above the cloud. Four orbits to the left at FL240 were flown for the SWS. An interrupted profile (P1) descent to 4000ft at point 40 on the AMPEP flight track was made. During the run (R1) at 4000ft along the AMPEP flight track the aircraft flew through the Cu cloud tops. The SWS was pointed forward to collect dirt on the window. The Buncefield fire plume could just be visually seen inland. At waypoint 45 a profile descent (P2) was made to fly below the air traffic corridor. The AMPEP track (R2) was then continued at 3500ft. A profile ascent (P3) over Devon was made from 3500ft to 8000ft. No significant indication of the plume was measured. A run (R3) at 8000ft was flown towards the plume location. A profile descent (P4) to 5000ft was then necessary to fly below an air traffic corridor. Run 4 then continued towards Chilbolton at 5000ft. A profile descent (P5) to 3000ft was made to try to observe any of the plume at lower levels. The following run (R5.1) at 3000ft was in and out of the cloud tops. This run was ended due to fuel limitations and a reciprocal run (R5.2) was made at 3000ft followed by R5.3. At this point Portland Bill danger areas were opened for us, as this was the area the plume was predicted to have dispersed to. A profile (P6) was made to try to observe any trace to the plume, followed by a short run at 5000ft. Increases in aerosol were seen when in cloud, as would be expected without the smoke plume. A profile climb (P7) to 7000ft, followed by a profile descent (P8) to 6000ft. The cloud physics probes during run (R7) at 6000ft showed size structure in the aerosol, again in the cloud. A profile descent (P9) to 3000ft was made to get below the cloud. During the run (R8) at 3000ft, some increases in aerosol were observed but no major changes in the chemistry. A profile climb to FL100 was made into the operating area to perform orbits. After the air traffic restriction was lifted (at FL100) a non-profile climb to FL200 was made and one orbit (O5) to the left at 45 degrees banking angle was made before having to land at Cranfield.

Instrument status

Core chem. – OK

SWS – OK, not sure that the window was coated with dirt as required.

Cloud physics - OK

Aircraft Scientist's Log

Oil Free Flight.

Flight No **B.148**.....

Date **12/12/05**.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
~10:00					Take off.
			034		Transit to NE.
10:01:10		FL200	063	52.5/0.6	Going higher to ensure above cloud.
					8/8 w below + hazy layer.
					wind 12ms ⁻¹ / 6°
100528		FL240	070	52.7/1.2	Above all cloud.
					wind 7ms ⁻¹ / 344°
					T-36.54, T _D -48.60
100730	01	FL240	040		220kts. turn to left.
100858	01end.				temp showing v. dry above w.
100959	02	FL240	340		turn to left.
101139	02end.				
101301	03	FL240	250		T-36.83, T _D -51.1
101446	03end.				turn to left.
101620	04	FL240	170		turn to left.
101804	04end.				all clear above, 8/8 w below.
101942	P1	FL240	293		profile descent to 4000ft.
					Leading to point 40 on AMPER flight track.
102343	P1int.	FL210	057	52.8/1.9	heading South.
102517	P1rec.	FL210	190	52.7/1.9	recommence profile.
103041	P1int.	FL150	190	52.2/1.8	Turning around as heading into restricted airspace at that altitude.
103251	P1rec.	FL150	0	52.3/1.7	Recommence profile.

Aircraft Scientist's Log

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
103730	Plint	FZ110			interrpt. O3 48.4 CO 162.9 - increase
103944	Plint	FZ110	182	52.5/1.8	Recommence profile.
104120		9500ft.	179	52.4/1.8	O3 65.4, CO 148.98 ppb. Wind 10ms ⁻¹ /40 Leaning towards front. On alt. plot increase in CO + decrease in O3 above 6200M
104510		5000ft.	181	52.1/1.8	21knts. T-1.25, T _D -1477
104614	Plend.	4000ft.			wind 13ms ⁻¹ /21°
104642	R1	4000ft.	179	52.1/1.8	possible smoke at of RH window?
105135		4000ft.	193	51.7/1.7	At top of W cloud.
10:54:49		4000ft.	191	51.5/1.6	O3 44.87, CO 109.75 ppb. Wind 11ms ⁻¹ /24°
105720		4000ft.	190	51.4/1.6	Starting top of W. O3 40.21, CO 119.12 Generally inst.
105841					going thro' bank cloud. at 10
110141				51.1/1.5	Out of cloud + in again
110344		4000ft.	238	51.0/1.3	Out again, above 818 W. Wind 15ms ⁻¹ /40°
110846					O3 37.93, CO 122.67, SO2 0.78 ppb.

Aircraft Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B.148**.....

 Date **12/12/05**.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
111030		4000ft.	238	50.8/10.8E	Grey cloud to right + now ahead.
111350		4000ft.	209	50.6/10.5	right turn at pt. 43 wind 17ms ⁻¹ 143. pilot wind 32 kts/034° 03 35.94, 10 129.1, 5020.87 holding steady. v. slight rise in 03. dark slivers of cloud at
112000		4000ft.	277	50.6/10.2	to right. v. low. ~373.5 kts/24. SWs pointing forward 90° PCASP concs. v. slowly increasing though v. small
112315				50.6/10.4	03 35.46, 10 128.12, 5020.77 (still const.)
112725					10 alt. before heading into cloud / grey area.
			210	50.6/10.9	still low grey area to right, plus thicker layer slightly higher.
112842				50.6/10.9	turn to left from at point 44. wind 17ms ⁻¹ 140° ⇒ turning away from grey area. due to air traffic restrictions. cloud above + below. flying in gap between. T 2.51, TD 0.8

Aircraft Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B.0148**.....

 Date **12/12/05**.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
113636	R1 _{end}	4000ft.			descending to get below airway at point 45 7/8 W.
113514					slight CO decrease 123.4 ppb. slight O ₃ increase 38.89 ppb.
113636	P2	4000ft.	223		descent to 3500ft.
113731	R2	3500ft.	222		
114000					Slight increase in CO + decrease in O ₃ to prev. levels CO 123.51, O ₃ 37.46
114243		3500ft.	209	49.9/2.04	Turning right at point 45. 8/8 W below. 8/8 Cloud base near between. Wind 15ms ⁻¹ 156° pilot: 26knts 150°
114406	R2 _{end}	3500ft.			
114417	P3				Profile climb to into cloud.
114559					
114640		4000ft.			O ₃ increase oppb. + corresponding CO decrease ⇒ coming out of boundary layer. O ₃ 42.4, CO 94.14, SO ₂ 0.78
114925	P3 _{end}	8000ft.			
114925	R3	8000ft.	271	49.9/2.7	In cloud. Cloud physics seeing ice particles during cloud.

Aircraft Scientist's Log

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Date ...12/12/05.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
115116		8000ft.	270	49.9/2.8	Out of cloud. In + alt of tops. No sign of smoke.
120236		8000ft.	352	50.2/3.7	Turning right to head N into Dean.
120703	R3end.				
120704	P4st.	8000ft.			
121024	P4end.	5000ft.		50.7/3.8	Turning right under air traffic corridor.
121204	R4	5000ft.	072.		Heading towards Chilbolton 8/8 W below, clear above
121700					42.88, 10117.91, 502 0.67 all baseline values
	R4end.				
121732	P5	5000ft.			Wind 11ms ⁻¹ / 58° T-0.8, T _D -4.0 in cloud.
		4500ft.			
		3600ft.	075.		Out of cloud, W below 6/8.
122012	P5end.	3000ft.	074.	50.8/3.0W	
		2500ft.	355	50.8/3.0W	Had to drop alt. due to air traffic.
122200					Some increase in aerosol + 10
122247		3000ft.			In + alt of cloud tops.
122435	R5.1	3000ft.	106	50.9/2.8	
122851	R5.1				Ending run. Not seeing aerosol. Hence have to return.

Aircraft Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B.148**.....

 Date **12/12/05**.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
123139	R5.2	3000ft.	260	50.8/12.7W	Wind 15ms ⁻¹ / 61° T 1.55, T _d -2.15 O ₃ 42.8, CO 114.9 SO ₂ 0.87 v. flat. small jumps but no significance.
124059					In cloud also seeing aerosol. increases + chem.
124140					Out of cloud aerosol normal again.
124156					In cloud small increase in PUFAs conts + upto 3µm sized. no pressure / changes in them. only see in cloud
125302	R5.3	3000ft.	063	50.0/13.3	
125945		3000ft.	078	50.2/12.8	CO 121.84, O ₃ 38.89 SO ₂ 0.77 ppb.
130152	R5.3end	3000ft.			preparing to sweep.
130208	P6				to try for aerosol.
130413	P6end	5000ft.			
130425	R6	5000ft.			

Aircraft Scientist's Log

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
130548					cloud physics small drops PCASP draw air
					03 42.0, 10 118.3 pp/h
130856	R6 cont.	5000ft.			1/7 W below. haze above.
				50-3/2.0W	turning right.
					T 0.29, T _D -0.32.
					them still normal.
131033	P7	5000ft.			climbing to try and get into smoke.
131140				50-3/2.2	into cloud
					enhancement of aerosol.
	#	6500ft.			out of top of cloud.
131313	P cont.	7000ft.			PCASP normal again.
131413	P8				descent to 3000ft.
					in cloud PCASP seeing high increase in aerosol.
	#				Intercepting to turn right and go back in cloud.
131814	P cont.	6000ft.			into cloud again.
	P8 cont.				Recommencing people descent.
131832	P7 st.	6000ft.			
131905		5880ft.			cloud physics seeing clean air.
131947					cloud phys now seeing aerosol ^{small increase}
		5890ft	089	50-3/2.4W	size structure variability rather than amplitude some turbulence.

Aircraft Scientist's Log

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
132135					aerosol enhanced
					by 4-10 factor above
					baseline. lots of
					structure in size.
132159	R7	6000ft.			
132207	P9	6000ft.			profile descent so can
					get.
132240		5000ft.			below cloud.
132447	P9	3000ft.			
132456	R8	3000ft.	86.	50.3/20W	Wind 13ms ⁻¹ 160°
					T2.49, T _D -2.54.
					Cloud physics seeming
					increasing during run
					v. small particles (<1µm)
133646		3000ft.	46	50.5/1.2W	Increase in CO spike and
					back to normal again.
					~ 3x ambient level.
133749		3000ft.	46	50.5/1.1W	O3 42.4, CO 114.8,
					SO2 0.78 ppb.
					wind 14ms ⁻¹ 158°
					T2.0°, T _D -4.99°
135423		3000ft.	85	50.6/1.1E	Core chem doing well.
135632					Increase in aerosol
					~ 10x ambient
					also looking thicker visually

Aircraft Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.48**.....
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Date **12/12/05**.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
					Instrument status:
					core chem all OK.
					cloud phys. all working
					SID PC reset several times.
					hence lost comp. log (have handwritten log)
					SWS - all OK.
					ACIES - under training all OK.
					SW - V15.
135714		3000ft.	86	^{50.6} 10.3	Starting to go in to cloud.
					still see seeing high number
					plus deplets on other
					insts.
					characteristic size structure
					changes alot, although concs.
					don't
					appear to be in polluted air.
					nothing really higher in alt.
					wind 12ms ⁻¹ 157°
					pilots: 28knts 161
135951		3000ft.	57	^{50.7} 10.7E	cloud phys. seeing more drops
					still seeing aerosol increase.
					N.B. core chem seeing NO change
					O3 41.83, CO 111.71, SO2 0.67
					still Have been seeing

Aircraft Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B.148**.....
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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
					elevations in aerosol since 13:46
140450					PCASP increase in conc. ~ 200/cc =
					~ 20x baseline
					still no change in core chem
1407					aerosol slowly decreasing
141118					levels ~ 100cc aerosol.
141158					going through tanker plume
					NOx is spiking + drop in O3.
					aerosol variations more likely due to patches of dust from tanker.
					~ 4/8 h ₂ - spiking in tops.
141758		3000ft.	16	51.3/1.5	in thick cloud + at again. wind 13ms ⁻¹ 146°
					T 0.52, T _d -2.41
142153					aerosol is ~ 60cc
					upto 300cc when passing through clouds.
142707	R8end	2800ft.			end of run to start to climb into operating area for orbit.
142745	P10	2500ft.	337	51.7/1.7	climb to FL100

Cloud Physics Log Jim Crawford B148

PSAP was run for the flight but the initial set up with 'hyperterminal' on the new laptop didn't work. The analogue output from the instrument is corrupt so no useful data was taken. The only numbers available are; 4 litres/sec for the flow, 1.00 for the start transmission and 0.584 for the end transmission.

The SID computer crashed, possibly caused by the Word log document. Each time all the previous log was lost. Resorted to handwritten log:

- 10:46 Run 1 start 4000'
 - CIPA running
 - SID1 running
 - FSSSP running
 - 2D-C, 2D-P & PCASP running
- 11:00 PSAP pump off during run through cloud tops (~10 minutes)
otherwise clear air with PCASP av conc. 44, av radius 0.09
- 11:24 PCASP counts slowly increasing as we travel westwards av conc. 125, av radius 0.09
- 11:36 descending to 3500' / qnh 1032
- 11:37:31 run 2 starts 3500'
- 11:41 SID1 computer reset itself
- 11:44 end of run 2
- 11:45 SID1 restarted with file no B148b
- 12:05 SID1 computer crashed again, logs lost
- 12:20 cloud tops – water drops max PCASP conc 350, some size structure
- 12:24:35 run 5 3000'
 - PCASP conc 40, mean rad 0.11
 - 2DC 2DP clear air
 - FSSSP 581
- 12:27:00 PCASP conc 40, mean rad 0.11
 - 2DC 2DP clear air
 - FSSSP 581

SID file now B148c
- 12:28:51 end run 5.1
- 12:34 run 5.2 – clear air
- 12:40 PCASP > 800 in cloud top
- 12:42 to 150 in cloud top
+ structure in size distribution
- 12:47 structure in size distribution
- 12:51 clear air – repositioning for smoke
- 12:53 run 5.3 starts

13:01 end run 5.3

13:02:08 profile 3000' to 5000'
run 6 5000'

13:09 end run 6

13:10:33 profile 7 fl50 to fl110, stopped at 13:13:13

13:14:13 profile 8 from fl70 started

13:18 5000' run 7 started

13:21:59 run 7 end

13:22 profile 9 to 3000'
13:24 end profile 9
start run 8 at 3000'
PCASP conc 31, rad 0.11
FSSSP 1027
2DC, 2DP zeros

13:38 run 8 3000'
PCASP conc 25, rad 0.09
FSSSP 1027
2DC, 2DP zeros

13:49 run 8 3000'
PCASP conc 43, rad 0.10
FSSSP 1027
2DC, 2DP zeros

13:56 run 8 3000'
PCASP conc 120, rad 0.09
FSSSP 1027
2DC, 2DP zeros

13:57 run 8 3000'
into cloud
PCASP conc 180, rad 0.09 – size distribution structure
FSSSP 1047
2DC, 2DP small drops

14:01 PCASP conc 160, rad 0.09 – size distribution structure
FSSSP 1047
2DC, 2DP zeros

14:08 peak
PCASP conc 400, rad 0.10 – size distribution structure
FSSSP 1048
2DC, 2DP zeros

14:12 peaks in PCASP conc [-500] coincident with cloud
FSSSP 1057
2DC, 2DP zeros

14:18 PCASP structure (again in cloud)

14:23 in cloud
PCASP conc 466, rad 0.17
FSSSP 1152
2DC, 2DP small water

14:27:07 end of run 8 3000'

14:27:45 profile 10, climb to fl60
in cloud, large drops, PCASP structure

14:29 clear of cloud

14:31 SID 'not responding' & 'no data' flags
clear air

14:33 small peak in PCASP [~40]

14:34 end of profile fl100
PCASP conc 10, rad 0.06
FSSSP 1241
2DC, 2DP zeros

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B148

Date: 12/12/05

B) 2D PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Completed	Comments
1) Transfer Bnnn.dat file from CD/DVD to PC	Y	
2) Zip up file on PC (Bnnn.zip)	Y	
3) FTP the zipped file (binary) from the PC to the directory SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA] on FLOODS	Y	
4) Log on to FLOODS		
5) unzip SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn.zip	Y	
6) In PVWAVE i) !PATH=!PATH+',MRFB:[PMS.PROC]' ii) CONVERT_SEADAS_FILE a) Input file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn.dat b) Output file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn_seadas.dat iii) exit	Y	Note the number of bad block reads and/or final numbers of blocks read & written Bad reads = 0
7) run MRFB:[PMS.SEADAS]READM200_FILE a) Default directory: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) Disk file name: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn_seadas.dat d) Comment string: e) Start time: 0 if unknown f) End time: 240000 if unknown g) Read 2DC: Y h) Read 2DP: Y i) Secondary data: Y j) FSP-SYNC: Y k) cmd.str: Y l) Auto time correction: N m) Full length secondary: N	Y	090000 160000
8) 2D image display and printing Quick look at image blocks if required In PVWAVE i) !PATH=!PATH+',MRFB:[PMS.PROC]' ii) WAVE> IMAGEDISPLAY a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) IWC plot: N d) Select probe: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP e) Start time: 0 if unknown f) End time: 240000 if unknown g) Time interval (sec): 0 for every image block nominal 5 sec		This section is optional Features to look for: 1) Noise on 2D-P – does it affect non-edge diodes (with potential to create spurious particle counts)? 2) Can you identify a dominant particle habit for the whole flight (eg. drops or crystals) 3)

Preparation of imagery for Core data product		
iii) WAVE> auto_image a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) Enter date: YYYYMMDD d) Enter start time 0 if unknown e) Enter end time 240000 if unknown f) Enter time interval (sec) between successive imaged blocks <p style="text-align: center;">10</p>	Creates files	Y
iv) exit PVWAVE	PMSDATA:	FAAM_YYYYMMDD_R0_Bnnn_2Dx-IMAGES.PS
ftp *.PS files from PMSDATA: to PC		Y
Load each into Ghostview or other pdf-converter		Y
Output as pdf file (70 dpi resolution) and append name prefix of CORE-CLOUD-PHY_ to converted files		Y
In O:\CloudPhysics Core data		
9) run MRFB:[PMS.SPEC2D.AUTO]PROCESS2D_AUTO		
a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) File generation: Hit enter d) Time correction: Time offset of the 2D data e) TAS: Y f) MFD directory: MFDDATA:Bnnn_MFDX g) Probe number: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP (0) Both 0 unless either probe known to be faulty h) Start time: 0 if unknown i) End time: 240000 if unknown j) Nominal averaging: 0.2 seconds for conversion to M5 k) Particle type: 8 if known to be in ice cloud 11 if known to be in water cloud 8 if known to be in mixed-phase 8 if unknown l) Coefficient choice: 2 m) Output root filename: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROC2D		Y
095000 151305 Note the particle type 8		
10) In PVWAVE		
i) enter: !PATH=!PATH+',MRFB:[PMS.PROC]' Note that the comma before "mrfb" is important! ii) WRITE_PROC2D_TO_M5, 'PMSDATA:BNNN_PROC2D.DAT', 'PMSDATA:BNNN_M5PROC2D' iii) exit		Y
11) MODIFY		
a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5proc2D b) Datset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: Enter modified MFD name d) Parameter description file: leave blank to use default		Y
12) CHECKS:		
i) Is 2DC/2DP IWC of comparable magnitude and well-correlated with Nevzorov TWC?		

CLLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B148

Date: 12/12/05

Processing Stage	Completed	Comments
1) Complete stage 7) in 2D processing Ensures Bnnn_FSP.DAT containing raw PCASP data is written to directory PMSDATA:	Y	
2) run MRFB:[PMS.PCASP]PROCPCASP_NEW a) Flight number: Bnnn b) File name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_FSP.DAT c) Root output name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP Produces PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.DAT (binary) PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.OUT (ascii) d) Minimum size channel: Default = 1 If smallest size channel are known to be noisy the value of the highest noise free channel to be entered here e) Calibration volume flow rate: Use the most recent value. Calibration files to be stored in ????? Entering zero gives default value = 1.0 cm ³ /sec f) Time correction: Same value as used in 2D processing stage 9 d) g) Start time: 0 if unknown h) End time: 240000 if unknown	Y	Note the min size channel Note the volume flow rate
3) In PVWAVE i) enter: !PATH=!PATH+',MRFB:[PMS.PROC]' Note that the comma before "mrfb" is important! ii) write_procpcasp_to_m5,'pmsdata:Bnnn_procpcasp.dat' ',pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procpcasp' iii) exit	Y	
4) MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procpcasp b) Datset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: Enter modified MFD name d) Parameter description file: leave blank to use default	Y	MFDB

ARIES flight log

Flight: B148

Location: OIL FLE SORTIE, SOUTH COAST ENGLAND

page 1 of

Date: 12/12/05

Operator(s): Newman, Rogers

Resolution: |

Gain A: 2

B: 4

Notes: *** FLOWN WITH UPPER AND LOWER BLANKS IN PLACE ***

DRS time	Flight ptrn	Filename	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Mir.	Det.	Win	Macro(s)	Comments
090600	—	B148B	C	61.2	31.0	13.0	-190.6	19.2	CH1 x 1	Ground tests
090730	—	B148C	C/O	61.3	31.2	13.0	-190.6	19.3	Z1 x 1	"
090855	—	B148D	C	61.1	31.0	13.1	-190.6	19.4	CH1 x 1	"
091007	—	B148E	C	61.1	30.9	13.3	-189.9	19.4	N1 x 1	"
092854	—	" F	C	61.1	31.1	14.4	-189.9	20.6	CH1 x 1	"
093008	—	" G	O	61.1	31.1	14.4	-189.9	20.7	Z1 x 1	"
093118	—	" H	C	61.2	30.3	14.3	-189.9	20.8	CH1 x 1	"
0948										TAKE OFF
095919	(In climb)	" I	C	61.2	26.8	14.4	-189.9	22.0	CH1 x 1	Profile prior to high level orbits
1000	"	" J	C	61.2	26.7	14.1	-189.9	22.0	N1 x 2	
100232	"	" K	C	61.1	26.6	14.2	-189.9	22.1	CH1 x 1	
100528		" L	C	61.0	25.8	14.0	-189.9	22.2	CH1 x 1	Climb end / begin of orbit
		" M	C						N1 x 2	Aborted
1008	01	" N	O	61.1	25.9	13.4	-189.9	22.3	Z1 x 2	
101010	02	" O	C	61.1	25.7	13.2	-190.6	22.3	CH1 x 1	At beginning of orbit
101120		" P	O	61.1	25.2	13.1	-190.6	22.4	Z1 x 1	End of orbit during macro
101237	03	" Q	C	61.5	25.4	12.8	-190.6	22.4	CH1 x 1	Orbit begins during
101353		" R	C/O	61.0	25.2	12.4	-190.6	22.4	Z1 x 1	

ARIES flight log

Flight: B148

Location:

page 2 of

Date: 12/12/05

Operator(s):

Resolution: 1

Gain A: 2 B: 4

Notes:

DRS time	Flight ptrn	Filename	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Mir.	Det.	Win	Macro(s)	Comments
101502	between orbits	B148S	C	61.2	24.9	12.1	-189.9	22.4	CH1 x 1	
101617		" T	O	60.9	23.9	12.2	-190.6	22.4	Z1 x 1	Started just before start of orbit
101752	OA	" U	C	61.1	24.4	11.6	-190.6	22.4	CH1 x 1	(left gap before this time after closing shutter)
104633	R1	" V	C	61.1	17.4	7.5	-190.6	22.4	CH1 x 1	Immediately after descent
104749	"	B148W	C	61.1	17.1	7.4	-190.6	22.4	N1 x 5	Haze to starboard
105244	"	" X	C	60.7	16.9	7.6	-190.6	22.5	CH1 x 1	Under Sc layer, few Cu below
105408	"	" Y	C/O	61.0	16.8	7.5	-190.6	22.5	Z1 x 5	Few few seconds shutter closed, in cloud at end
		Z								Restart software
110131	"	C148A	C	71.1	30.7	8.3	"	22.8	CH1 x 1	
110245	"	" B	C	70.9	30.7	8.2	"	"	N1 x 5	In cloud at start, then above it
110908	"	" C	C	71.0	30.5	9.1	"	23.0	CH1 x 1	Broken cloud below, Sc above
111035	"	" D	O	70.9	30.7	9.0	-189.9	23.1	Z1 x 5	Looks like thin stratus above
111625	"	" E	C	70.9	30.5	10.0	"	23.3	CH1 x 1	(after 1 min idle time)
111736	"	" F	C	70.8	31.0	10.3	"	23.4	N1 x 5	Largely clear below
112232	"	C148G	C	70.9	30.9	11.0	"	23.6	CH1 x 1	
112346	"	" H	O	70.9	30.7	11.2	"	23.7	Z1 x 5	Sc overhead
112950	"	" I	C	70.8	30.7	11.7	"	24.0	CH1 x 1	
113110	"	" J	C	71.0	30.7	11.7	"	24.1	N1 x 5	Thin Sc below

ARIES flight log

Flight: B148

Location:

page 3 of

Date: 12/12/05

Operator(s): Newman, Rogers

Resolution: 1

Gain A: 2 B: 4/2

Notes:

DRS time	Flight ptrn	Filename	Shttr	HBB	CBB	Mir.	Det.	Win	Macro(s)	Comments
113607	R1 cont.	C148K	C	70.7	30.8	12.0	189.9	24.3	CH1 x 1	run interrupted, descent to 3500' during cal
113742	R2	C148L	C	70.8	30.8	12.4	"	24.4	CH1 x 1	repeat cal.
113912	"	C148M	O	70.9	30.8	12.7	"	24.5	Z1 x 5	thicker stratus stratus above
(Time check)	"	"	X	ARIES clock 114834	at DRS 114830				CH1 x 1	end of cal coincides with end of run, profile
114944	R3	" N	O/C	71.0	30.8	13.5	"	25.0	CH1 x 1	
115116	"	" O	O	71.0	30.8	13.5	"	25.1	Z1 x 5	Above Sc clear above
115721	"	" P	C	71.0	30.9	13.9	"	25.4	CH1 x 1	passing through occasional cloud (after min idle) in turn at beginning
120033	"	" Q	C	70.9	30.8	14.2	"	25.5	CH1 x 1	Gain B 4/2 as was too high
120248	In turn	C148 R	C	70.9	30.7	14.2	"	25.6	N1 x 2	In turn prior to profile
121042		" S	C	71.0	30.7	14.3	"	26.0	CH1 x 1	Immediately after profile
121220	R4 (FL 050)	" T	O	70.8	31.1	14.4	"	"	Z1 x 5	Looks clear above
122023	3000' S/L	" U	C	70.9	31.0	14.8	"	26.3	CH1 x 1	end of zenith coincides with end run (at end of profile)
122328	"	" V	C	70.9	31.0	14.6	"	26.4	CH1 x 1	
122445	R5.1	" W	C	70.8	31.0	14.4	"	26.5	N1 x 4	Above broken cloud in turn at the end
122933		C148 X	C	70.8	30.8	14.6	"	26.7	CH1 x 1	In turn
123100	3000' S/L R5.2	" Y	F/O	70.8	31.0	14.6	"	26.8	Z1 x 5	Started recording just before start of run
123645	"	" Z	C	70.9	31.1	14.9	"	26.9	CH1 x 1	immediately following zenith (thin stratus above)

ARIES flight log

Flight: 6148

Location: B148 South coast of England

page 4 of

Date: 12/12/05

Operator(s): Newman, Rogers

Resolution: 1

Gain A: 2 B: 2

Notes: Blanks in place, training flight

DRS time	Flight ptrn	Filename	Shttr	HBB	CBB	Mir.	Det.	Win	Macro(s)	Comments
123918	RS.2	D148A	C	71.0	30.9	14.6	189.9	27.1	CH1 x 1	
124045	"	" B	C	71.1	30.6	15.1	"	"	N1 x 5	Sometimes in cloud otherwise above broken Sc
124614	"	" C	C	71.0	31.0	15.3	"	27.3	CH1 x 1	
124849	"	" D	C/O	71.0	31.4	15.3	"	27.4	Z1 x 3	Largely clear above Max alt during run
125306	Run 5.3	" E	C	70.9	30.8	15.6	"	27.6	CH1 x 1	<u>V.</u> low interferogram signal
125428	"	" F	C	71.0	30.9	15.6	"	27.6	N1 x 5	
130013	"	" G	C	71.3	30.4	15.9	"	27.8	CH1 x 1	
1301.44	" / PG	" H	O	71.0	30.8	16.0	"	27.9	Z1 x 3	profile to 5000' soon after starting
130532	R6 5000'	" I	O/C	71.2	30.3	16.0	"	28.0	CH1 x 1	
130650	"	" J	C	71.1	30.9	15.9	"	28.1	N1 x 3	Turn at 1309, P7A F110 at end of data
131848	R7 6000'	D148K	C	71.0	31.0	16.1	"	28.6	CH1 x 1	
132011	"	" L	O	70.9	31.1	16.3	"	28.6	Z1 x 3	In cloud; descent started 1322.07
132508	R8 3000'	" M	C	70.7	30.9	16.1	"	28.8	CH1 x 1	
132626	"	" N	C	70.8	30.7	16.4	"	28.8	N1 x 3	few Cu below, broken Sc above
133012	"	" O	C	70.7	31.0	16.2	"	28.9	CH1 x 1	
133147	"	" P	O	70.8	30.4	16.2	"	29.0	Z1 x 3	
133626	"	" Q	C	70.8	30.2	16.4	"	29.1	CH1 x 1	
133747	"	D148 R	C	70.7	30.8	15.8	"	29.1	N1 x 4	Hazy

FLOTc terminated

ARIES flight log

Flight: 6148

Location: S. coast England

page 5 of

Date: 12/12/05

Operator(s): Newman, Rogers

Resolution: 1

Gain A: 2 B: 2

Notes:

DRS time	Flight ptrn	Filename	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Mir.	Det.	Win	Macro(s)	Comments
134241	R8	D148S	C	71.0	30.8	16.2	189.9	29.3	CH1 x 1	
134430	"	" T	O						Z1 x 4 ABORTED	shutter closed at beginning *SCANNER SWITCH ACCIDENTALLY FLIPPED*
134834	"	" U	O	64.1	30.0	16.5	"	29.9	Z1 x 3	
135321	"	" V	C	61.1	30.1	16.6	"	29.6	CH1 x 1	
135443	"	D148 W	C	60.9	29.9	16.2	"	29.7	N1 x 4	Looks clear below; then into cloud 135720
135932	"	" X	C	60.9	29.9	16.1	"	29.8	CH1 x 1	
140117	"	" Y	O	61.0	29.7	16.2	"	29.9	Z1 x 4	V. thin Sc above, then some higher Ci.
140724	"	" Z	C	61.1	29.4	16.3	"	30.0	CH1 x 1	
140957	"	E148 A	C	70.6	30.9	16.1	"	30.1	CH1 x 1	
141132	"	" B	C	71.0	30.6	16.5	"	31.0	N1 x 4	Hazy otherwise clear below in some diffuse cloud
141648	"	" C	C	71.0	30.7	16.4	"	30.3	CH1 x 1	
141857	"	" D	O	71.0	30.8	16.2	"	30.3	Z1 x 4	In cloud at times
142514	"	E148 E	C	71.0	30.6	16.8	"	30.5	CH1 x 1	
142652	" / P10	" F	C	70.8	30.8	16.7	"	30.5	N1 x 2	end of run 142707 (3000') P ↑ F2060 142745
143509	P2100	" G	C	70.8	31.1	16.8	"	30.7	CH1 x 1	Immediately following p-tilt
143643		" H	C	71.4	30.9	16.4	"	30.8	N1 x 2	

"SMOKE FLIGHT - FROM HONOLULU HEMISPHERE OIL PLUME"

SWS FLIGHT LOG SHEET

Flight #	B 148	Date	2/2/05	Operator(s)	JRK + MG	log page	1	of	5
Time	Run id	Alt/FL	MIRR Pos	Int Times		Remarks			
				Vis	NIR				

0938		Engine Start	Pre-flight	checks	OK				
094804		T/O	CANFIELD						
095033		Trans. Climb	900FT	150	1000	(Reset shutter needed) (1 sec sample period)			
0951			(A)			Reset time from Huerco			
095450						Peltier +20m (Pelt 3 & 4 off) (Temp +15)			
100252			Start	Camera	Recording (LP)				
100730	ORBIT 1	240	6°F	150	150	Start Orbit 1 (45°) Temp L (0.2 Sample Period)			
100858	ORBIT 2					End Orb 1 (Keep Sample Period & Integ times const for all orbits)			
100959	ORBIT 2	240	6°F	150	150	Orbit 2 start (45°) 0.2 sec Sample period			
						Dark Cal			
101139						End Orbit 2 Dark Cal			
101304	ORBIT 3	FL241	6°F	150	150	Start Orbit 3 (45°) [0.2 sec Sample Period]			
101446						End Orbit 3			
101502						Dark Cal (Temp +13°C)			
101620	ORBIT 4	FL241	6°F	150	150	Start Orbit 4 (to Port)			
101804						End Orbit 4			
101828						Dark Cal			
						Port SWS to Forward [To collect smoke particles / used during flight]			
101942	P1	FL242	090°F	150	150	Start Profile Detector P1 1000'			
102209						Dark Cal			
102218	P1	FL245	090°F	100	1000	Sample Period 1.00 sec [Temp +13°C]			
102243	P1 interrupt	FL240	"						

Once H. Noefork out Zen angle v 78°

SWS FLIGHT LOG SHEET

Flight #	B 148	Date	12/12/05	Operator(s)	JRK / MGF	log page	2 of 5
Time	Run id	Alt/FL	MIRR Pos	Int Times		Remarks	
				Vis	NIR		

102517						Recommend P1.
102658						Dark Cal
102711	P1 ↓		90 F	30	1000	Start Measurement [Temp +14]
104435	P1 ↓	(1013) 4.9 kft	90 F	30	1000	Sample Period 1.00 sec [Temp +15] [Peltier 1 off on] (3 R4 off)
104614	P1 End	(1013) 3 kft	90 F	30	1000	End P1
		(7000')				
104642	R1	7000'	90 F	30	1000	[Sample Period 1.00 sec] [Temp +16]
105140	On AMPER ROUTE					Around SE the S coast England Under cloud now (~7000' above; cloud layer below)
1059						Passing thro. real cloud tops (lower layer)
1100						" " more continuous cloud tops
111130	R1	7000'	90 F	30	1000	Sample Period 1.00 sec [Temp +13C]
111720						← Slightly 'greyish' dust ahead to R (from Mexican Sc). - little evidence of smoke plume yet (Sc Mixed with Sc layers from smoke weakening cold front nearby S)
111930	Patches small Cu below 1/8 Layers CM & CH above.					[Temp +12C]
1125						→ Temp +11C (All Peltiers off) Darker/thicker patches of Cu ahead (about this alt.)
112851						→ RESET TIME on SWS FROM HERCE.
113636	END RUN 1 / Start P2.					Stop Run 1 & descend to 3500' → 3500'
113731	RUN 2	3500'	90 F	30	1000	End P2 Commence RUN 2. (WIND 052/25 kts) (Sample period) [HERCE 050/16 mph] 1/sec [Temp +13C]
114406		3500'				End Run 2
114417	P3 ↑	3500'	90 F	30	1000	Start P3 [Temp 14C]
114926	END P3 /	FL 050	90 F	30	1000	End P3; Start R3 at FL 050.

START R3

SWS FLIGHT LOG SHEET

Flight # **B 148** Date **12/2/05** Operator(s) **DK/MC** log page **3** of **5**

Time	Run id	Alt/FL	MIRR Pos	Int Times		Remarks
				Vis	NIR	

1158	R3	FL080	90F	30	1000	→ Temp +16 [Peltier 1 & 2 on] [Sample period 1 sec]
120036						Start Cal ⁿ started
12010	R3	FL080	90F	30	1000	Start Measurement. T = +16°C:
120703	End R3	FL080	90F	30	1000	End R3 / Start P + ↓ 3000'
120704	Start P4					
121024	End P4	FL050				← End P4
121204	Start R4	FL050	90F	30	1000	Start R4 [Temp +15°C] ← End R4
121732	Start P5	FL050				Start P5 ↓ 3000'
122013	End P5	3000'	90F	30	1000	End P5 [Temp +14°C] (2.5kft 1013). Sample 1.00 sec.
122220	(Increase in CO mix ratio [1221 -] Decrease in O ₃ mix ratio [1222] seen from H ₂ ACE display.					Change in CO/NO _x - change in conc ⁿ /size from C. Physics (as passing thro' cloud) (No denudation action for ATC)
122435	Start R5.1	3000'	90F	30	1000	Start R5 [Temp +14°C]
122851	End R5.1	3000'				End R5 [Temp +13°C]
12930						→
						Will now head W towards Devon, then continue with AirPef track clockwise along S. Coast & around Kent L ₂ Anglia
123139	Start R5.2	3000'	90F	30	1000	Start R6 [Sample period 1.00 sec]
123500						Temp +12; Peltiers off mix ratio
124046						↳ into cloud; CO _a 115 ↑ 135 ppb & correspondingly decrease in O ₃ mixing ratio for 1-18 mins seen on H ₂ ACE.
124450						Temp +14 [Peltiers 1 & 2 on]
125033						End R5.2. Heading to Danger Areas to NE of current pos where we've been allowed special access from HM Cabinet!

12A-15
8012

SWS FLIGHT LOG SHEET

Flight #	B148	Date	12/12/05	Operator(s)	DJK / MG	log page	4 of 5
Time	Run id	Alt/FL	Mirr Pos	Int Times		Remarks	
				Vis	NIR		

125302	R5.3	3000'	90F	30	1000	Start R5.3
125330						End SWS Camera I Tape
125400						Start Camera II Tape
130153	End R5.3					End R5.3
130209	Start P6					Start P6 / 5000'
130435	End P6 / Start R6	5000'	90F	30	1000	End P6, Start R6 (Above Portland Bill)
						[Sample Period 1.00 Sec] [Temp +12°C]
130856						End R6, Turning Will pass thro' plume on ascent (?) to FL110
131033	Start P7	5000'	90F	30	1000	Start P7
						Cloud Tops 6500'; little increase in Cloud Physics info / areas
131313		7.2kft				End P7 [Temp +11°C]
131413	P8 ↓		90F	30	1000	Start P8 [Peltier all off]
						Jump Aerosol } c. Physics when in cloud
131614		(6000) 5.4kft → 13mb				End P8
131832	R7.	6000'				Start R7. (SW Portland Bill)
1						Structure in size, not huge amount of CCV
132201	End R7 / Start P9	6000'				End R7, Start P9 → 3000'
132455	End P9 / Start R8	3000'	90F	30	1000	End P9, start R8 at 3000'
132703						Start Cal ⁿ (Dark View)
132730	R8	3000'	90F	30	1000	Start Measurement [Temp +13°C]
						Sample 1.00 Sec
133130						[Temp +14°C] Peltier's 1 & 2 on
135500	R8	3000'	90F	30	1000	Temp +12°C
135625						Thicker aerosol patch here (Cloud Physics visually) (x10 above base value) Characteristic 'size' value 0.1 → 3.0 μm
1400						into aerosol plume here BUT (no increase in 2DP/2DC / other c. Physics data, nor an core chem data.)

SWS FLIGHT LOG SHEET

Flight # **B 148** Date **12/12/95** Operator(s) **JRK / Mgr** log page **5** of **5**

Time	Run id	Alt/FL	MIRR Pos	Int Times		Remarks
				Vis	NIR	

140530						Start Dark Current Cal.
140551	R8	3000'	90F	30	1000	Start Measurement
1406						PCASP ↑ Aerosol conc ⁿ over last 2 mins (200-300/cc) (→ base ~20/cc)
140850				→		Temp +11°C [ALL Peltiers off]
142640				→		Temp +14°C [Peltiers 1 & 2 on]
142707	End R8	3000'	90F	30	1000	End R8
142715	Start P10					
142837				→		Synchronise HALICE / SWSTime Cloud Top 1500'
143300						Prepare for orbits new; M
1434	R8	10000'	6F	150	150	Start Dark Cal (x2)
14345p						Start Measurement [Sample period 0.2 sec]
143538				→		Stop recording data for new, prepare for orbits (Several more)
143930						Start climbing ↑ (CAMS DOME (Mgr))
144220						Start Dark Cal
144227			6F	150	150	Start Measurement
144400	ORBIT 5	FL200	6F	150	150	Start Orbit 5 (45° L)
144520				←		End Orbit
144556						Start Dark Cal.
144600						Start Measurement
144835				←		Stop Recording Tape
1450						Stop SWS Measurement, SWITCH OFF & prepare for landing
150450				←		LAND (CRASHFIELD)
094804						
5h 16m 46sec						

ORBIT 5 6°F 150 150 0.2 sec Sample P.

Flight Manager's Instrument Status Log

Flight No. **B** 147

Date: 9th December 2005

Instrument	Operated	Instrument	Operated
<u>Navigation</u>		<u>Cloud Physics</u>	
INU	Y	Probes	
XR5M GPS	Y	FFSSP	Y
Cruciform GPS	N	PCASP	Y
Satcom C	Y	2D-P	Y
Satcom H	Y	2D-C	Y
<u>Thermometers</u>		Cloudscope	N
De-Iced Temp	Y	SID 1	Y
Non De-Iced	Y	SID 2	N
Heimann	Y	HVPS	N
<u>Hygrometers</u>		CIP25	N
G. Eastern	Y	CIP100	Y
J. Williams	Y		
Nevzorov	Y		
TWC	Y		
FWVS	N	Racks:	
<u>Radiometers</u>		INC	N
Upper Clear	Y	CCN / CPC	Y
“ Red	Y	CVI	N
“ Silicon	Y		
“ JO1D	N	<u>Aerosol</u>	
Lower Clear	Y	PSAP	Y
“ Red	Y	Nephelometer	N
“ Silicon	Y	Filters	N
“ JO1D	N	AMS	N
<u>Large Radiometers</u>			
TAFTS	N		
MARSS	N		
DEIMOS	N	<u>Others:</u>	
ARIES	n	NIR TDLAS	N
SWS	Y	2BT O3	N
<u>Chemistry</u>		VACC	N
Ozone	Y	PEROXIDE	N
SO2	Y	Formaldehyde	N
NOX	Y	ADA	n
CO	Y	CPI	n
ORAC	N	NOxy	N
PAN	N	PTRMS	N
PERCA	N	Bag Sampling	N
WAS	N	Tube Sampling	N

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B148

Date: 12th December 2005

Instruments

Johnson Williams faulty throughout whole flight – DRS reading zero most of the time.

Aircraft

Satcom H Calls

3 answered

3 faulty line

10 out of range all by Met O

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B148:

Log	Reason
Core Chemistry	pre flight only, unmanned operation on auto calibrate so no In Flight log
PSAP	No operator listed but Flight Manager's Instrument Status log lists PSAP

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

- 3 x Forward Facing Cameras
- 3 x Down/Forward Facing Cameras

Digital8 video recordings from this flight reside with :

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